

Towards Optimization-Driven Haptic Teleoperation for Magnetic Capsule Locomotion

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Abstract. This work-in-progress paper presents a shared-control framework for safe magnetic capsule navigation based on optimization-informed rendering. A QP-CLF-CBF controller ensures task execution and obstacle avoidance, while Lagrange-multiplier-derived signals support adaptive behavior and future feedback rendering. Preliminary simulations motivate open questions at the intersection of robotics, haptics, and human-robot interaction.

1 Introduction

Small-scale magnetic robotic systems are being explored for operations in confined and hard-to-access environments, with applications in targeted drug delivery, endovascular procedures, and environmental remediation. In these scenarios, magnetic agents are actuated wirelessly by external magnetic sources, such as electromagnets or permanent magnets.

Because of the nonlinear magnetic interaction and the presence of safety-critical constraints, fully autonomous operation is often difficult to justify. Human-in-the-loop control is therefore appealing, as it combines operator judgment with autonomous assistance. Shared control offers a principled way to balance human authority and robotic autonomy. Prior works have addressed control allocation for the safe navigation of electromagnetic microrobots [4], while recent optimization-based approaches have encoded task and safety objectives in a unified framework [8,10,9,7]. These approaches suggest a natural route to generate multisensory feedback informed by the underlying optimization problem.

We adopt here this perspective for the safe navigation of a magnetic capsule actuated by an external permanent magnet mounted on a robotic manipulator. Although this actuation setup and its controllability properties have been studied previously [6,2], shared-control architectures and feedback rendering for this platform remain largely unexplored, and are therefore addressed here.

2 Methodology

2.1 Optimization-based Controller

The considered scenario is reproduced in a virtual environment (see Fig. 1). A robot manipulator carries a permanent magnet and moves it above a maze-like workspace filled with aqueous medium and populated by obstacles. The objective is to drive a magnetic capsule to a desired location while avoiding collisions.

Fig. 1: Shared Control architecture for safe teleoperation of the magnetic capsule.

The magnetic interaction is described through a dipole–dipole approximation [5]. Denoting by \boldsymbol{x} the system state with capsule position and robot configuration, the controller is then formulated as a quadratic program (QP) that computes the optimal joint velocity command \boldsymbol{u}^* by combining task-regulation and safety objectives. In particular, a Control Lyapunov Function (CLF) $V(\boldsymbol{x})$ promotes convergence to the desired capsule position, while N Control Barrier Functions (CBFs) $B_i(\boldsymbol{x})$, $i = 1, \dots, N$, enforce obstacle avoidance [1].

The CLF is defined from the capsule position error with respect to a desired reference, which can be generated either autonomously or by the human operator through the teleoperation interface. The CBFs are instead defined through superquadric functions approximating the workspace walls and obstacles. As a result, the QP drives the capsule toward the commanded target while autonomously reshaping the motion whenever safety constraints become dominant.

2.2 Optimization-informed Signals for Rendering

Solving the QP also yields the Lagrange multipliers associated with its constraints, indicating how strongly each constraint affects the optimal solution. These can be exploited as optimization-informed signals for feedback rendering and adaptive assistance [3,9,7]. In particular, the multipliers associated with the CBF constraints provide a measure of how strongly obstacle-avoidance requirements modify the commanded motion. The same information can also be reused to *adapt* the controller online: the CLF relaxation weight is modulated according to the average CBF multiplier activity as $w_\delta(\boldsymbol{x}) = w_{\delta,\max} - (w_{\delta,\max} - w_{\delta,\min}) \sigma(\bar{\lambda})$, where $\bar{\lambda}$ is the average of the CBF-related multipliers and $\sigma(\lambda)$ is a sigmoid activation function. This reduces the emphasis on trajectory regulation when safety becomes dominant, while generating an interpretable signal that can be rendered to the operator.

3 Preliminary Results

Preliminary simulations on a circular reference trajectory were conducted to analyze the evolution of the Lagrange multipliers during obstacle-constrained navigation and to assess the effect of the proposed adaptive CLF relaxation. As shown in Fig. 2, the adaptive slack-weight update improves the tradeoff between

Fig. 2: Comparative simulations on trajectory tracking of the magnetic capsule for different weights of the CLF slack variable: (a) evolution of the obstacle avoidance CBF value; (b) planar trajectory of the capsule.

tracking and safety: the CBF remains positive along the whole trajectory (red line in Fig. 2a), while the tracking error is lower than with fixed maximum or minimum slack weight (blue line in Fig. 2b). These results support the use of Lagrange multipliers as informative signals for both adaptive control and feedback rendering in shared-control settings.

4 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

A first question concerns the **interpretability** of optimization-informed feedback, since it is still unclear which form of the Lagrange multipliers information is most meaningful to the operator during shared control. A second question concerns the **rendering strategy**, since different mappings from optimization variables to haptic cues should be assessed in terms of transparency, workload, and perceived agency. These questions motivate exchange with other disciplines. Haptics expertise can support the design of effective rendering strategies, while human-robot interaction and cognitive ergonomics can help define user studies and evaluation metrics, including workload, predictability, and trust.

5 Conclusions

This paper presented a framework for safe magnetic capsule navigation, leveraging optimization-informed signals that can be used in haptic teleoperation setting. The approach combines an optimization-based controller for task execution and obstacle avoidance with a rendering strategy that exploits Lagrange multipliers, to convey safety-related intervention and support adaptive behavior. Preliminary simulation results suggest that these signals are informative both for controller adaptation and for future operator feedback.

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